

Studies on Kinetics of the Oxidation of Mandelic Acid by Ceric Salts

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Kinetics of the reaction between ceric salts (sulphate and perchlorate) and mandelic acid have been studied. The order is found to be 1 after 1 to 2 minutes from mixing. The reaction is faster when ceric perchlorate is used as oxidant than when ceric sulphate is used. The activation energy in the case of oxidation by ceric sulphate is found to be 6.4 kcal. The H^+ ion retards the reaction rate. The oxidation appears to proceed through the initial formation of an activated complex and subsequently through free radicals.

Krishna and Tewari¹ have studied the oxidation by Ce(IV) of mandelic acid. When the acid is in excess, the reaction is found to be of the second order. The present communication deals with the kinetics of oxidation of mandelic acid when there is an excess of oxidant. Both ceric sulphate and ceric perchlorate have been used as oxidants.

EXPERIMENTAL

The materials employed were of the highest purity available. Ceric ammonium sulphate was an E. Merck (G.R.) product and its solution in sulphuric acid was directly prepared. Standardisation of the ceric sulphate solution was carried out by iodometric method. Stock ceric sulphate solution employed was in $2N-H_2SO_4$. Ceric perchlorate was prepared by the electrolytic oxidation of Ce(III) perchlorate by the method suggested by Smith². AnalaR ceric ammonium nitrate was used as the starting material.

Nitrates were eliminated during the process. The salt was heated with perchloric acid and H_2O_2 to reduce it to the trivalent stage. Then it was taken to fumes of perchloric acid and finally converted into ceric perchlorate by the electrolytic oxidation. The solution was stored in a refrigerator until required for use when it was diluted to the desired concentration. It was then standardised against sodium oxalate and also by iodometric method.

Perchlorates of sodium and magnesium were prepared by the action of the respective carbonates (Na_2CO_3 , E. Merck and $MgCO_3$, Pattinson's brand) on $HClO_4$ (E. Merck). The solution of organic acid was standardised by titration against a standard NaOH solution (against phthalate).

Mandelic acid and ceric solutions were taken in two 250-ml conical flasks, kept in the thermostat for 1 hour, and then rapidly mixed. Aliquot parts were withdrawn at suitable intervals and analysed for residual ceric by iodometric method.

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3097.

2. *Anal. Chem.*, 1955, 27, 1144.

The products formed on oxidation of mandelic acid were tested frequently (up to about 8 hours) and benzaldehyde was found as the only reaction product. On leaving the acid, however, overnight with excess of the oxidant, benzoic acid was also found as a reaction product in addition to benzaldehyde. This is obviously due to the oxidation of benzaldehyde which appears to be a slow process. In our studies, we have followed the reaction up to about 85% consumption of the acid. We are therefore concerned with oxidation to benzaldehyde, *i.e.*, a consumption of 2 Ce(IV) ions per mandelic acid molecule.

Order of Reaction.—Oxidation of mandelic acid was studied in presence of excess of ceric salts. In most of the cases the amount of Ce(IV) was about twice that of mandelic acid. Oxidation with about 2.5-fold excess of Ce(IV) was also followed. These runs were taken at 15° as the reaction was fast at 25°. The experimental data were plotted on the basis of first order and second order rate equations. It was found that plot of $\log a/(a-x)$ [where 'a' is the initial concentration of Ce(IV) and (a-x), the concentration of Ce(IV) at time 't'] against 't' was linear (except for the first 1 to 2 minutes of mixing the reactants), indicating that the reaction was first order after about a minute. This disturbance is possibly due to some side reaction which progressively slows down as the complex formation approaches completion [when α -hydroxy-acid is mixed with Ce(IV) salt, a transient colour is formed which disappears in about a minute]. The first order reaction constants have been calculated from the slope of the $\log a/(a-x)$ vs. t plot. Figs. 1 and 2 show typical plots. The results are recorded in Table I (A and B).

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Effect of H⁺ ions on the Reaction.—The reaction was retarded by the hydrogen ion. The curve, $\log K$ against pH, is linear within the limits studied and the slope is unity (Fig. 5). Column 6 of Table I shows the product of $K[H^+]$ which is fairly constant,

TABLE I

Oxidation of mandelic acid by ceric sulphate.

No.	Concentration, Mandelic acid.	Concentration, Ceric sulphate.	pH.	K (min ⁻¹).	K[H ⁺].
A. Temp. = 25°.					
1	0.0125M	0.025M	1.08	0.1393	0.01240
2	0.0125	0.025	1.10	0.1483	0.01179
3	0.0125	0.025	1.16	0.1508	0.01154
4	0.0025	0.005	1.20	0.1535	0.00983
5	0.0230	0.050	1.22	0.1853	0.01116
6	0.0100	0.020	1.28	0.1871	0.00998
7	0.0125	0.025	1.30	0.2308	0.01151
B. Temp. = 16°.					
1	0.0100	0.0281	0.98	0.06525	
2	0.0080	0.0225	1.04	0.06909	
3	0.0125	0.0250	1.10	0.08956	

Effect of Dilution of the Reactants.—The rate constants were determined with different concentrations of the reactants. The results indicate that when the effect of H⁺-ion is taken into account, the rate constant is the same. From the results it appears that when the oxidant is in excess (about 2-fold or 3-fold), the rate constant is the same, independent of dilution.

FIG. 3

Influence of Salts on Reaction Velocity.—Different salts, viz., NaClO₄ (M), Mg(ClO₄)₂ (M), MgSO₄ (M), and Na₂SO₄ (M), were added to the reaction mixture, the proportion of mandelic acid and ceric salts being in the ratio of 1:2. Na₂SO₄ and MgSO₄ were found to retard the rate of reaction. The results are recorded in Table II (A & B). The rate of oxidation, however, remained the same in presence of NaClO₄ or Mg(ClO₄)₂.

TABLE II

Effect of salts on the oxidation of mandelic acid by ceric sulphate.

No.	A. Mandelic acid = 0.0125M. Ceric sulphate = 0.025M. pH = 1.36. Temp. = 25°.		B. Mandelic acid = 0.0125M. Ceric sulphate = 0.025M. pH = 1.30. Temp. = 31°.	
	Salt (M conc.).	K (min ⁻¹).	Salt (M conc.).	K (min ⁻¹).
1	Nil	2.506 × 10 ⁻⁴	Nil	2.506 × 10 ⁻⁴
2	Na ₂ SO ₄	1.535	Na ₂ SO ₄	1.632
3	MgSO ₄	1.019	MgSO ₄	1.984
4			NaClO ₄	2.506
5			Mg(ClO ₄) ₂	2.506

Influence of Temperature on the Reaction Velocity.—The reaction velocities were measured at three different temperatures. All the three experiments were performed at identical pH and log K was then plotted against $1/T$ (Fig. 4). From the linear plot the energy was calculated. The activation energy was found to be 6.4 kcal./mole.

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

Oxidation of Mandelic Acid by Ceric Perchlorate.—The reaction was found fast at 25°. The kinetics of oxidation were studied only at 5°. The results fit the first order equation. The plots of $\log a/(a-x)$ vs. t are shown in Fig. 6. The first order rate constants calculated are recorded in Table IVA. The oxidation has been studied with different acid concentrations. The increase in acidity retards the

oxidation process as found in the case of oxidation with the ceric sulphate.

TABLE III

Oxidation of mandelic acid by ceric sulphate at diff. temperature.
pH = 1.10. Other condition same as in Table II.

Temp.	..	25°	15°	5°
$K(\text{min}^{-1})$	..	0.1483	0.08956	0.07484

TABLE IV

Oxidation of mandelic acid by ceric perchlorate.

Mandelic acid = 0.0166M. Ceric perchlorate = 0.0353M. Temp. = 5°.

No.	A. In absence of salt.		B. In presence of salt.	
	HClO_4 .	$K (\text{min}^{-1})$.	Salt.	$K (\text{min}^{-1})$.
1	0.902N	2.763×10^{-2}	Nil	0.9212×10^{-2}
2	1.371	0.9212	M-NaClO ₄	0.9212
3	1.712	0.6909	M-Mg(ClO ₄) ₂	0.9212

Table IVB shows the rate constants for the oxidation in the presence of NaClO₄ and Mg(ClO₄)₂. The results indicate that the salts have no effect on the oxidation rate.

DISCUSSION

Duke and Forist³ studied the oxidation of glycols by ceric ion and suggested the first step in the oxidation to be the transfer of electrons from the glycol to metal in the highest valence state when these combined in the form of a chelate:

The strong electron pull of the ceric ion causes the removal of an electron from the organic chelating agent, resulting in the breaking of the C-C bond. Subsequent steps, according to these authors, are free radical reactions. In connection with the oxidation of α -hydroxy-acids by manganic pyrophosphate, Waters and Levesley⁴ proposed that radical RCHOH was first formed as a result of the decomposition of the complex between manganic pyrophosphate and α -hydroxy-acid. The radical RCHOH formed is readily oxidised to the final product. In case of the oxidation of α -hydroxy-acids by ceric ion, it is very likely that a complex is formed between ceric ion and the α -hydroxy-acid which results in the formation of a free radical. The subsequent reactions are radical reactions.

As already mentioned, Krishna and Tewari¹ found the reaction to be of second order. In the present case, the reaction is found to be of first order. It has been pointed out that these authors studied the kinetics with α -hydroxy-acid in large excess, whereas in the present case the oxidant is in excess. When there is an excess of ceric salt, the radical reacts with the ceric ion; on the other hand, when the acid is in large excess, the reacting species is a complex. The mechanisms proposed are shown below.

When ceric ion is in excess, the different steps of the oxidation process are:

MA⁻ is mandelate ion, MĀ, mandelate radical, and M', a free radical.

From equations A, B, C, and D, we have

$$\frac{d[\text{Ce}]}{dt} = k_1 [\text{MA}^-] [\text{Ce}^{IV}] - k_2 [\text{CeMA}] + k_3 [\text{M}'] [\text{Ce}^{IV}] \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{d[\text{CeMA}]}{dt} = k_1 [\text{MA}^-] [\text{Ce}^{IV}] - k_2 [\text{CeMA}] - k_3 [\text{CeMA}] \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\frac{d[\text{MA}]}{dt} = k_3 [\text{CeMA}] - k_4 [\text{MA}] \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\frac{d[\text{M}']}{dt} = k_4 [\text{MA}] - k_5 [\text{M}'] [\text{Ce}^{IV}] \quad \dots (4)$$

If $k_2 \gg k_3$ by stationary state method, we have

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce}^{IV}]}{dt} = k_5 [\text{M}'] [\text{Ce}^{IV}] = k [\text{Ce}^{IV}]$$

When α -hydroxy-acid is in excess, the different steps are:

The rate equations are:

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = k_1 [\text{MA}^-] [\text{Ce}^{IV}] - k_2 [\text{CeMA}] + k_5 [\text{M}'] [\text{CeMA}] \quad \dots (1)$$

$$-\frac{d[\text{CeMA}]}{dt} = k_1 [\text{MA}^-] [\text{Ce}^{IV}] - k_2 [\text{CeMA}] - k_3 [\text{CeMA}] - k_5 [\text{M}'] [\text{CeMA}] \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\frac{d[\text{MA}]}{dt} = k_3 [\text{CeMA}] - k_4 [\text{MA}] \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\frac{d[\text{M}']}{dt} = k_4 [\text{MA}] - k_5 [\text{M}'] [\text{CeMA}] \quad \dots (4)$$

If stages (B) and (D) are slow, under stationary condition we have

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce}^I]}{dt} = k_5 \frac{k_1}{k_2} [\text{MA}^-] [\text{Ce}^{IV}] = k' [\text{MA}^-] [\text{Ce}^{IV}]$$

So we see that it is not surprising that the reaction is a second order one when the α -hydroxy-acid is in excess. On the other hand, when the oxidant is in excess, the reaction is of first order.

In view of the fact that the SO_4^{2-} ions form stronger complexes, it is natural to expect that the ceric sulphate will react slower than the ceric perchlorate. To the same cause one can attribute the retardation of the reaction when Na_2SO_4 or MgSO_4 is added. The oxidation by ceric perchlorate and also $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ is hardly affected by addition of sodium perchlorate or magnesium perchlorate. The fact that in case of the oxidation by $\text{Ce}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$

or $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ (vide Tables II and IVB) the rate constant is independent of ionic strength, lends support to the assumption that the oxidation proceeds through free radicals. Had the reaction been ionic, the oxidation by ceric perchlorate would have been affected by the change in ionic strength.

FIG. 6

From the rate expression, based on the mechanism proposed by us, it will appear that the reaction is controlled by step (D). The activation energy determined would then correspond to this reaction step for which one would expect a low value. The experimental value of 6.4 kcal. further justifies the proposition.